

Strengthening One Health and Resilient Food Systems in Africa: Strategic Insights and Lessons Learned on Surveillance and Biosecurity from G7 Chief Veterinary Officers

Abstract

The One Health approach highlights the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health, making it essential for African nations to adopt strategies that build resilience in their food systems. Key elements like zoning and biosecurity are vital in controlling livestock diseases, ensuring food security, and safeguarding public health. Zoning involves designating disease-free regions to manage outbreaks while maintaining trade, whereas biosecurity focuses on farm sanitation, managing animal movements, and vaccination efforts to reduce disease spread. Strengthened surveillance systems, which incorporate diagnostic tools, digital technology, and community involvement, are crucial for early detection and quick responses to emerging threats. Additionally, sustainable livestock practices, such as rotational grazing and using resilient breeds, contribute to long-term resilience and environmental stability. This paper emphasizes the importance of integrated strategies to strengthen One Health and establish sustainable food systems in Africa, promoting both economic stability and public health as a strategic insight and advice by the G7 Chief Veterinary Officers to developing countries. Their advice serves as a roadmap for countries to strengthen animal health systems, reduce the risk of pandemics, and build more resilient food systems in Africa.

Keywords

One Health, Zoning, Biosecurity, Surveillance Systems, Sustainable Livestock Practices, Food Security, Africa, Public Health, Livestock Diseases, Resilience

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Introduction

The increasing recognition of the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health within the One Health framework has become more relevant than ever. This is particularly important in African countries, where agriculture and livestock are vital to the economy. To protect public health and ensure food security, it is essential to implement zoning and biosecurity measures. Zoning involves classifying regions based on their disease status to manage outbreaks effectively, while biosecurity practices aim to curb the spread of infectious diseases within livestock populations. By enhancing surveillance systems, enforcing biosecurity protocols, and promoting sustainable livestock management, African countries can build resilient food systems that benefit people,

animals, and the environment (World Health Organization, 2023).

The G7 Chief Veterinary Officers (CVOs) Meeting, coordinated by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), provides a crucial platform for discussing global challenges in animal health, biosecurity, and food systems (WOAH, 2024). The 2024 G7 CVOs Meeting in Italy, part of Italy's G7 presidency, focuses on addressing critical issues such as zoonotic diseases, antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and the impact of climate change on agriculture and livestock. This meeting emphasizes the One Health approach, which integrates solutions across human, animal, and environmental health to tackle emerging global health challenges (G7 Presidency, 2024).

During the 2024 meeting, discussions are geared toward enhancing international cooperation, fostering knowledge exchange, and developing strategic measures to build resilient food systems that can withstand health crises. The goal is to strengthen veterinary frameworks within G7 countries while also providing support to other nations, especially in the Global South, to improve their animal health infrastructure (WOAH, 2024). This meeting in Italy offers a significant opportunity for global alignment towards health security, positioning the veterinary sector as a key player in achieving a safer and more sustainable future.

Zoning as a Disease Management Strategy

Zoning plays a critical role in managing livestock diseases. It involves defining specific regions according to their disease status to contain outbreaks and limit the spread of infectious diseases (FAO, 2020). For instance, the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) has applied zoning strategies to control Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) in African countries, allowing unaffected regions to continue trade while restricting livestock movement from affected areas (WOAH, 2019). This approach not only protects animal health but also stabilizes local economies that depend heavily on livestock trade.

Zoning has proven effective in controlling diseases like African Swine Fever (ASF) in some African regions (Penrith et al., 2022). Establishing disease-free zones enables countries to maintain international trade while minimizing disease risks. However, effective implementation of zoning requires coordinated efforts among veterinary services, governments, and other stakeholders to ensure compliance and effectiveness.

Strengthening Biosecurity Measures

Biosecurity is essential to prevent the introduction and spread of infectious diseases in livestock populations. These measures include managing animal movements, maintaining farm hygiene, and implementing vaccination programs. Enforcing biosecurity protocols can significantly reduce the risk of disease transmission and contribute to the resilience of food systems (Rich & Perry, 2022).

Biosecurity practices have been particularly successful in controlling zoonotic diseases like avian influenza and brucellosis, which pose risks to human health (Munyeme et al., 2021). Establishing quarantine stations and checkpoints to regulate animal movements is especially critical in regions with porous borders, where transboundary animal diseases can spread rapidly (FAO, 2020). At the farm level, practices like regular disinfection, isolating sick animals, and using protective gear can prevent outbreaks. Training programs can raise awareness about biosecurity's importance in reducing zoonotic diseases among livestock farmers.

Strengthening Surveillance Systems

Robust surveillance systems are key to detecting and responding to emerging diseases. Improving surveillance involves upgrading diagnostic capabilities, training veterinary personnel, and leveraging digital tools for real-time reporting of disease outbreaks (Fèvre et al., 2022). In many rural African regions, limited veterinary infrastructure hinders timely detection and response to disease outbreaks.

Combining community-based surveillance with digital technologies can fill this gap. Mobile apps for reporting animal health concerns, alongside GIS mapping, can identify disease hotspots and facilitate rapid responses (FAO, 2020). Regional collaboration through bodies like the African Union's Inter-African Bureau for Animal Resources (AU-IBAR) is also vital for sharing information and coordinating responses to cross-border animal diseases (AU-IBAR, 2019). Improved surveillance systems enable better risk assessments, allowing policymakers to allocate resources more effectively and ensure food safety.

Promoting Sustainable Livestock Practices

Sustainable livestock practices are essential for building resilient food systems and minimizing zoonotic disease risks. These practices include rotational grazing, integrating livestock with crop production, and using locally adapted breeds resistant to diseases (McDermott et al., 2021). Such practices also benefit environmental health by preventing overgrazing and soil degradation, supporting the One Health goals.

Beyond environmental benefits, sustainable livestock practices can enhance economic

resilience by reducing reliance on external inputs like feed and veterinary medications. For example, integrating Azolla as a feed supplement can lower costs and improve local resilience (Ampofo et al., 2024). Moreover, organic farming practices can produce healthier livestock products, reducing the risk of antimicrobial resistance, a concern in both human and veterinary medicine (WHO, 2020).

The Role of One Health in Food System Resilience

The One Health approach stresses the need to manage human, animal, and environmental health collectively to achieve sustainable development. Strengthening biosecurity and surveillance in livestock management aligns with One Health's goals by reducing the risk of zoonotic spillovers that could trigger pandemics (Karesh et al., 2021). By adopting a One Health approach, African nations can bolster their food systems' resilience, ensuring food security despite disease outbreaks and environmental challenges.

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for strong health systems capable of identifying and managing emerging threats. Investing in zoonotic disease prevention through zoning, biosecurity, and surveillance is crucial for avoiding future pandemics and maintaining the health of both people and animals.

Lessons from the G7 Chief Veterinary Officers Meeting Organized by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH)

The G7 Chief Veterinary Officers (CVO) meeting, organized by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), presents a platform for key stakeholders to address global challenges in animal health, biosecurity, and food systems. Here are the key lessons from the meeting:

1. Importance of Coordinated Global Action in Animal Health

- **Lesson:** The meeting emphasized the need for coordinated action among countries to tackle transboundary animal diseases and zoonotic threats. The CVOs highlighted that animal diseases do not respect borders, necessitating collaboration to ensure biosecurity and food safety.
- **Application:** Countries can adopt the practice of sharing surveillance data and

adopting harmonized protocols for disease control to strengthen regional and global responses to emerging health threats.

2. Strengthening Biosecurity Measures

- **Lesson:** The G7 CVOs underscored the critical role of robust biosecurity measures in preventing the spread of animal diseases, especially in livestock production systems. This includes protocols for farm hygiene, movement control of animals, and vaccination strategies.
- **Application:** African countries, and other regions, can draw from the G7's emphasis on stringent biosecurity measures to protect their livestock industries and prevent zoonotic diseases from spilling over to humans.

3. Leveraging Technology for Enhanced Surveillance

- **Lesson:** The meeting highlighted the potential of digital technologies, such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and mobile reporting tools, to strengthen disease surveillance systems and ensure real-time data sharing. This enables early detection and rapid response to emerging diseases.
- **Application:** Incorporating digital tools in veterinary practices can improve disease tracking, allowing countries to detect outbreaks swiftly and mitigate their spread, ultimately protecting both animal and human populations.

4. The Role of One Health in Combating Zoonotic Diseases

- **Lesson:** The CVOs reinforced the One Health approach, which recognizes the interconnection between human, animal, and environmental health. The COVID-19 pandemic was a key discussion point, illustrating how zoonotic diseases can have profound impacts on global health.
- **Application:** Adopting a One Health approach can help countries to design integrated strategies for preventing zoonotic diseases, ensuring that the health of animals, humans, and ecosystems is considered together.

5. Investment in Veterinary Services and Capacity Building

- **Lesson:** A key outcome of the meeting was the emphasis on investing in veterinary infrastructure and capacity-building initiatives. There is a recognized need for well-trained veterinary personnel and properly equipped laboratories to enhance diagnostic and response capabilities.
- **Application:** For many developing nations, this serves as a reminder to prioritize investments in veterinary education, training, and infrastructure, to build resilient health systems that can cope with the demands of modern animal health management.

6. Importance of Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) in Veterinary Health

- **Lesson:** The G7 CVOs stressed the value of public-private partnerships in driving innovations and mobilizing resources for disease prevention and control. Partnerships with the private sector can also help in the distribution of vaccines and the implementation of biosecurity protocols.
- **Application:** By fostering public-private collaborations, countries can access new technologies, financing, and expertise to enhance their animal health management strategies, especially in the face of resource constraints.

7. Promoting Sustainable Livestock Production for Long-term Food Security

- **Lesson:** Discussions highlighted the role of sustainable livestock management practices in ensuring the long-term resilience of food systems. Practices such as rotational grazing, sustainable feed practices, and resilient animal breeding can reduce the risks of disease outbreaks and ensure environmental sustainability.
- **Application:** Integrating sustainable livestock practices can help countries not only protect their animal populations but also maintain ecological balance and enhance food security.

8. The Need for a Unified Response to Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR)

- **Lesson:** AMR was a significant topic of concern during the meeting, with CVOs stressing the need for global cooperation to combat the misuse of antibiotics in livestock production. This includes implementing policies to regulate antimicrobial use and promote alternatives.
- **Application:** Countries should adopt and enforce regulations around antimicrobial use in veterinary medicine and invest in research for alternative treatments, such as probiotics and vaccines, to reduce reliance on antibiotics.

9. Enhancing Preparedness for Future Pandemics

- **Lesson:** The COVID-19 pandemic served as a critical case study during the meeting, emphasizing the need for preparedness plans that can address future pandemics originating from animal sources. The G7 CVOs discussed building resilient health systems that can quickly adapt to such crises.
- **Application:** Developing robust emergency preparedness and response plans will ensure that countries are better positioned to manage future pandemics, thus safeguarding public health and minimizing economic disruptions.

10. Regional and International Collaboration for Knowledge Exchange

- **Lesson:** The G7 meeting provided a platform for sharing best practices and innovative strategies for animal health management. The discussions highlighted the importance of continuous knowledge exchange between countries and regions.
- **Application:** Regular regional meetings and partnerships with international organizations, such as the WOAH and the FAO, can help countries stay updated with the latest advances in veterinary science and implement proven strategies for animal health and food safety.

Conclusion

Zoning and biosecurity are key strategies for enhancing surveillance systems, supporting One Health, and building resilient food systems in African countries. By creating disease-free zones, implementing biosecurity protocols, and investing in surveillance infrastructure, African nations can reduce the impact of animal diseases on public health and food security. Additionally, promoting sustainable livestock practices helps ensure long-term resilience, benefiting both communities and the environment.

As African countries face challenges from emerging diseases and climate change, integrating these strategies into national policies is critical for sustainable development and safeguarding future generations' health. Following this strategic plan, African nations can effectively implement zoning and biosecurity measures, mitigate disease risks, strengthen food system resilience, and support the One Health framework.

These lessons from the G7 Chief Veterinary Officers Meeting highlight the importance of a collaborative, technology-driven, and One Health-centered approach to safeguarding animal health and food systems globally. Countries can draw from these insights to strengthen their own animal health frameworks, ensuring resilience against emerging threats.

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